

MODELS DESCRIBED BY BISTOCHASTIC QUADRATIC OPERATORS

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Abstract:

The article introduces the concept of a bistochastic quadratic operator acting in the simplex S^{n-1} . Necessary and sufficient conditions for bistochasticity are obtained. It is noticed that the set of all bistochastic quadratic operators acting in S^{n-1} , forms a polyhedron. The dynamical and statistical (ergodic) properties of the trajectories of bistochastic quadratic operators are investigated.

Keywords:

stochastic operator, bistochastic operator, ergodic theorem.

Аннотация:

В статье вводится понятие бистохастического квадратичного оператора, действующего в симплексе S^{n-1} . Получены необходимые и достаточные условия для бистохастичности. Замечено, что множество всех бистохастических квадратичных операторов, действующих в S^{n-1} , образует многогранник. Исследованы динамические и статистические (эргодические) свойства траекторий бистохастических квадратичных операторов.

Ключевые слова:

Стохастический оператор, бистохастический оператор, эргодическая теорема.

Annotatsiya:

Мақолада S^{n-1} симплексида бистохастик квадратик оператор тушунчаси киритилган. Бистохастикликнинг зарурийлик ва етарлилик шартлари олинган. S^{n-1} симплексида барча бистохастик квадратик оператор тўплами кўпёкни

ташқил қилиши кўрсатилган. Бистохастик квадратик операторларнинг динамик ва статистик (эргодик) хоссалари ўрганилган.

Kalit so'zlar:

Стохастик оператор, бистохастик оператор, эргодик теорема.

§ 1. Necessary conditions for bistochasticity of quadratic operators

Let $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in S^{n-1}$. From [1], by $x_{\downarrow}$ denote point $x_{\downarrow} = (x_{[1]}, \dots, x_{[n]}) \in S^{n-1}$ where $x_{[1]} \geq \dots \geq x_{[n]}$ – point coordinates $x \in S^{n-1}$, ordered non-increasing. Point $x_{\downarrow}$ called permutation x non-increasing. If $x, y \in S^{n-1}$ and the inequalities hold $\sum_{i=1}^k x_{[i]} \leq \sum_{i=1}^k y_{[i]}$, $k = \overline{1, n}$, then they say that y majorizes x and writes $x \prec y$. These terms and designations were introduced by Hardy, Littlewood and Poya [2]. Obviously, for any $x \in S^{n-1}$ we have

$$\left(\frac{1}{n}, \dots, \frac{1}{n}\right) \prec x \prec (1, 0, \dots, 0).$$

As is known [1], a necessary and sufficient condition for the fulfillment of the relation $x \prec y$ is the existence of a bistochastic matrix P , such that $x = Py$. Recall that the matrix $P = (P_{ij})_{i, j = \overline{1, n}}$ is called bistochastic (doubly stochastic) if

$$P_{ij} \geq 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^n P_{ij} = 1.$$

Therefore, for a bistochastic matrix P fair attitude $Px \prec x$ for any point $x \in S^{n-1}$. The latter property can be taken as a definition of bistochasticity P [1]. Following this, we will retain the term bistochasticity for an arbitrary continuous (generally speaking, nonlinear) operator $V : S^{n-1} \rightarrow S^{n-1}$, satisfying the condition

$$Vx \prec x. \tag{1}$$

for all $x \in S^{n-1}$.

In particular, the quadratic stochastic operator $V : S^{n-1} \rightarrow S^{n-1}$ is defined by the equality

$$x'_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} x_i x_j, \quad k = \overline{1, n}, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{ij,k} = P_{ji,k} \geq 0$ и $\sum_{k=1}^n P_{ij,k} = 1$, when (1) is fulfilled, it is called bistochastic (hereinafter b.q.o.).

Theorem 1. If $V: S^{n-1} \rightarrow S^{n-1}$ - b.q.o., then the coefficients $P_{ij,k}$ satisfy the following conditions:

$$\text{a) } \sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} = n, \quad \forall k = \overline{1, n} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{б) } \sum_{j=1}^n P_{ij,k} \geq \frac{1}{2}, \quad \forall i, k = \overline{1, n} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{в) } \sum_{i,j \in I_t} P_{ij,k} \leq t, \quad \forall t, k = \overline{1, n}, \quad (5)$$

where $I_t = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_t\}$ - an arbitrary subset of the set $I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, containing t elements.

Remark. Condition (3) and inequality (4) are consequences of (5). Indeed, in (5) we put $t = n$, i.e. $I_n = \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Then

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} \leq n, \quad \forall k = \overline{1, n}. \quad (9)$$

On the other side, $\sum_{k=1}^n P_{ij,k} = 1$. That's why

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} \right) = n^2. \quad (10)$$

If at least one strict inequality holds in (9), then we obtain $\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} \right) < n^2$,

which contradicts (10). So, from (5) it follows (3).

Let us show that (5) also implies (4). We have

$$n = \sum_{i,j=1}^n P_{ij,k} = \sum_{i,j=2}^n P_{ij,k} + P_{11,k} + 2 \sum_{j=2}^n P_{1j,k} .$$

Taking into account (5), we have that $\sum_{i,j=2}^n P_{ij,k} \leq n - 1$

and find

$$P_{11,k} + 2 \sum_{j=2}^n P_{1j,k} \geq 1$$

or

$$2 \sum_{j=2}^n P_{1j,k} \geq 1 + P_{11,k} \geq 1.$$

Hence, $\sum_{j=1}^n P_{1j,k} \geq \frac{1}{2}$ and in general, $\sum_{j=1}^n P_{ij,k} \geq \frac{1}{2}$ for all i, k .

§ 2. DESCRIPTION OF THE CLASS OF BISTOCHASTIC QUADRATIC OPERATORS

Matrix $T = (t_{ij})$, $i, j = \overline{1, n}$ is called substochastic if $t_{ij} \geq 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} \leq 1$. If in the last inequality for all $i = \overline{1, n}$ has an equal sign, then T called stochastic.

Let $A = (a_{ij})$, $i, j = \overline{1, n}$ symmetric matrix, and $a_{ij} \geq 0$.

Consider the following equation for T .

$$A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T'), \tag{11}$$

where T' - transposed matrix.

Below we will deal with the condition for the solvability of Eq. (11) in the class of substochastic matrices.

Let G_n – index permutation group $\{1, \dots, n\}$. For $\pi \in G_n$, by A_π denote the matrix $A_\pi = (a_{\pi(i)\pi(j)})$, $i, j = \overline{1, n}$, which is called matrix permutation A . The following sentences follow from the definitions:

- $(A_\pi)_{\pi^{-1}} = A$;

- If A – symmetric, then A_π also symmetrical;
- If A – substochastic, then T_π also substochastic;
- $(A + B)_\pi = A_\pi + B_\pi$, $(\lambda A)_\pi = \lambda \cdot A_\pi$.

It follows from the listed properties that if T is a solution to equation (11), then T_π is a solution to the following equation:

$$A_\pi = \frac{1}{2}(T + T').$$

Theorem 2. Let $A = (a_{ij})$ - symmetric non-negative $(a_{ij}) \geq 0$ matrix. For the existence of a substochastic matrix $T = (t_{ij})$ satisfying Eq. (11), it is necessary and sufficient that

$$\sum_{i,j \in I_k} a_{ij} \leq k \tag{12}$$

for anyone $k = \overline{1, n}$ and any set k indices $I_k = \{i_1, \dots, i_k\}$.

Remark. Substochastic matrix T , whose existence is guaranteed by Theorem 2, is, generally speaking, not unique.

EXAMPLE. For matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0,1 & 0,3 & 0,4 \\ 0,3 & 0,1 & 0,5 \\ 0,4 & 0,5 & 0,4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

the set of solutions to the equation $A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T')$ in the class of substochastic matrices is

$$T_\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 0,1 & \alpha & 0,9 - \alpha \\ 0,6 - \alpha & 0,1 & 0,3 + \alpha \\ \alpha - 0,1 & 0,7 - \alpha & 0,4 \end{pmatrix},$$

where $0,1 \leq \alpha \leq 0,6$.

It is easy to see that the set of solutions to the equation

$$A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T') \tag{13}$$

is a convex polytope. Indeed, substochastic matrices $T = (t_{ij})$, $i, j = \overline{1, n}$, whose coefficients satisfy the following system of linear inequalities:

$$\begin{cases} 0 \leq t_{ij} \leq 1 \\ t_{ij} + t_{ji} = 2a_{ij} \\ \sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

form a convex compact bounded by the plane.

From (13) it follows $(Ax, x) = (Tx, x)$, где $(\cdot; \cdot)$ – scalar product R^n .

Really,

$$(Ax, x) = \frac{1}{2}((T + T')x, x) = \frac{1}{2}[(Tx, x) + (T'x, x)] = (Tx, x) \tag{14}$$

Let's return to the study of bistochastic quadratic operators.

According to Theorem 1, if $V : S^{n-1} \rightarrow S^{n-1}$ – b.q.o., then

$$\sum_{i, j \in I_t} P_{ij, k} \leq t,$$

where $I_t = \{i_1, \dots, i_t\}$ – arbitrary set indices, and for $t = n$ equality holds.

Assume

$$A_k = (P_{ij, k})_{i, j=1}^n$$

and using the corollary from Theorem 2, we find the stochastic matrices T_k such that

$$A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T'), \quad k = \overline{1, n}.$$

According to (14), we have

$$\sum_{i, j=1}^n P_{ij, k} x_i x_j = (A_k x, x) = (T_k x, x).$$

So if V – b.c.o., then we can find the stochastic matrices $T_1, \dots, T_n$, such that

$$Vx = ((T_1 x, x), (T_2 x, x), \dots, (T_n x, x)).$$

Let us prove the inequality:

$$\min_{1 \leq i \leq n} x_i \leq (Tx, x) \leq \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} x_i, \quad \forall x \in S^{n-1},$$

or in the accepted notation:

$$x_{[n]} \leq (Tx, x) \leq x_{[1]}, \quad \forall x \in S^{n-1}. \quad (15)$$

where T – any stochastic matrix.

Really, if $t_{ij} \geq 0$ и $\sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} = 1$, то

$$x_{[n]} \leq \sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} x_j \leq x_{[1]}$$

for any $x \in R^n$. In particular, for $x \in S^{n-1}$ we have

$$(Tx, x) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n t_{ij} x_i x_j = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \left(\sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} x_j \right).$$

Considering $x_i \geq 0$, $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 1$ and the previous inequality, we obtain the required inequality (15).

Theorem 3. Let $A = (a_{ij})$ – non-negative symmetric matrix. Then, to satisfy the inequality

$$x_{[n]} \leq (Ax, x) \leq x_{[1]}, \quad \text{for all } x \in S^{n-1},$$

necessary and sufficient to

$$\sum_{i,j \in I_t} a_{ij} \leq t,$$

for all $I_t = \{i_1, \dots, i_t\}$, where $t = \overline{1, n}$, and with $t = n$ equality holds.

Proof.

1. Sufficiency follows directly from the corollary of Theorem 2 and inequality (15).

2. Necessity. Let $1 \leq t \leq n$ и $I_t = \{i_1, \dots, i_t\}$ – arbitrary set t indices. We put $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in S^{n-1}$, where

$$x_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{t}, & \text{for } i \in I_t \\ 0, & \text{for } i \notin I_t \end{cases}$$

then for $t < n$ we have $x_{[n]} = 0, x_{[1]} = \frac{1}{t}$. By hypothesis, we have

$$0 \leq (Ax, x) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij}x_i x_j = \frac{1}{t^2} \cdot \sum_{i,j \in I_t} a_{ij} \leq \frac{1}{t}$$

we get

$$\sum_{i,j \in I_t} a_{ij} \leq t, \quad t < n.$$

If $t = n$ then $x_{[n]} = x_{[1]} = \frac{1}{n}$. Hence,

$$\frac{1}{n} \leq \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i,j \in I_t} a_{ij} \leq \frac{1}{n},$$

i.e.,

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij} = n.$$

So, both of the theorems 2 and 3, we can assert that for matrices $A = (a_{ij})$ c nonnegative elements satisfying the inequality

$$x_{[n]} \leq (Ax, x) \leq x_{[1]} \tag{16}$$

on the whole simplex S^{n-1} in a sense is equivalent to stochasticity. More precisely, (24) is equivalent to the existence of a stochastic matrix $T = (t_{ij})$, such that

$$A + A' = T + T'.$$

Problem: For which symmetric matrices A the inequality holds

$$x_{[n]} + x_{[n-1]} + \dots + x_{[n-k+1]} \leq (Ax, x) \leq x_{[1]} + \dots + x_{[k]}, \tag{17}$$

for all $x \in S^{n-1}$, where k – some natural number $1 \leq k \leq n$?

For $k = 1$ the answer to this problem is given by Theorem 3. To solve the problem in the general case, we introduce the notation:

$$\mathfrak{S}_k = \left\{ T = (t_{ij}), i, j = \overline{1, n}: 0 \leq t_{ij} \leq 1, \sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} = k \right\}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n$$

$$U_k = \left\{ A = (a_{ij}): a_{ij} = a_{ji}, A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T'), T \in \mathfrak{S}_k \right\}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n$$

Further U_k will be called symmetrization $\mathfrak{S}_k$.

Theorem 4. If $A \in U_k$, then for any $x \in S^{n-1}$ the inequality holds:

$$x_{[n]} + x_{[n-1]} + \dots + x_{[n-k+1]} \leq (Ax, x) \leq x_{[1]} + \dots + x_{[k]}.$$

Let us list some simple properties of the sets U_k , which we need. Across E the order matrix $n \times n$, all elements of which are 1.

Theorem 5. The following propositions are true:

- i) $A \in U_k \Leftrightarrow E - A \in U_{n-k}, k = \overline{1, n-1}$;
- ii) $U_k \cap U_l = \emptyset$, for $k \neq l$;
- iii) $U_n = \{ E \}$;
- iv) $A \in U_k \Rightarrow \frac{p}{k} \cdot A \in U_p, 1 \leq p \leq k$;
- v) $U_k + U_l \supset U_{k+l}, k + l \leq n$;
- vi) U_k - polyhedron.

Proof. i) Let $1 \leq k \leq n-1$ and $A \in U_k$. From the view $A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T')$, where

$T = (t_{ij}), 0 \leq t_{ij} \leq 1, \sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} = k$, hence $E - A = \frac{1}{2}[(E - T) + (E - T)']$, moreover, the

elements $E - T = (1 - t_{ij})_{i,j}$ satisfy the conditions: $0 \leq 1 - t_{ij} \leq 1$ и $\sum_{j=1}^n (1 - t_{ij}) = n - k$.

That's why $E - A \in U_{n-k}$.

ii) If $A \in U_k$, then $\sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij} = n \cdot k$. That's why $U_k \cap U_l = \emptyset$, for $k \neq l$.

iii) If $A \in U_k$, then follows $0 \leq a_{ij} \leq 1$ for all $k = \overline{1, n}$. If $A \in U_n$, i.e. $\sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij} = n^2$

ensures that $a_{ij} = 1$. Hence, $U_n = \{ E \}$.

iv) Insofar as $A \in U_k$ и $A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T')$. Then $\frac{p}{k} \cdot A = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{p}{k} T + \frac{p}{k} T' \right]$ moreover

$\frac{p}{k} A \in \mathfrak{S}_p$. That's why $\frac{p}{k} A \in U_p$.

v) Let $k + l \leq n$, $A \in U_{k+l}$ and $A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T')$.

We put $A_1 = \frac{k}{k+l} A$, $A_2 = \frac{l}{k+l} A$. Obviously, $A_1 \in U_k$, $A_2 \in U_l$ and $A = A_1 + A_2$

. That's why $U_{k+l} \subset U_k + U_l$, moreover $k, l \geq 1$ – the inclusion is strict, which is easy to see from the following example. We put

$$B_1 = B_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $B_1, B_2 \in U_1$, but $B_1 + B_2 \notin U_2$.

vi) Consider the mapping $\tau: \mathfrak{S}_k \rightarrow U_k$, where

$$\tau: T \rightarrow A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T'). \tag{23}$$

It is easy to see that τ – affine and surjective mapping. It's clear that $\mathfrak{S}_k$ polyhedron. That's why $U_k = \tau(\mathfrak{S}_k)$ is also a polyhedron.

In Theorem 2, a necessary and sufficient condition was obtained for $A \in U_1$, expressed in terms of coefficients (a_{ij}) .

The problem naturally arises: find a similar condition equivalent to $A \in U_k$, for a given $k = \overline{1, n}$.

There are general methods that allow one to obtain necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of solutions to systems of linear inequalities, and in the case of existence, find the so-called basic solutions. However, these general methods for system (24) lead to cumbersome and ineffective expressions. It is easy to

calculate that the maximum number of independent solutions of the system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} t_{ij} + t_{ji} = 2a_{ij}; & i > j \\ \sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} = k; & i = \overline{1, n} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

equal $\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}$. Therefore, the set of solutions to the equation

$$A = \frac{1}{2}(T + T'), \quad T \in \mathfrak{S}_k \text{ forms a solvability polytope at most } \frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}.$$

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